

Using Convolutional Neural Networks to Analyze and Detect Key Points of Objects in Image

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Abstract: The article discusses the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for analysis and detection of key points of objects in images, in particular hands. The mathematical representation of the principles of CNNs work explains the keypoint detection process, and the conducted experiments show the significant influence of lighting conditions and frame rate (frame per second - FPS) on detection accuracy and processing delay. The results confirm that increasing illumination up to 500 lux and frame rates up to 60 FPS improve accuracy and reduce latency, although detection accuracy decreases in low light. The findings highlight the importance of lighting and frame rate optimization to achieve high real-time performance.

Key words: Industry 5.0, Collaborative Robot, Mobile Robots, Work Area, Computer Vision, CNNs.

Introduction

In today's manufacturing environment, which is evolving towards the concept of Industry 5.0, the cooperation between man and machine is becoming a key factor in achieving new levels of efficiency and safety. One of the important components of this process is the integration of collaborative manipulator robots capable of high-precision interaction with people and surrounding objects [1]-[11]. To implement such interaction, it is necessary to provide robots with the ability to accurately recognize and analyze the objects they work with, which involves reliable and fast detection of key points in image [12]-[18]. Various image analysis methods can also be used here [19]-[41]. In this context, the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) becomes particularly relevant, as they are able to provide high-quality image analysis, which is necessary for accurate positioning and manipulation of objects. CNNs demonstrate exceptional results in detecting key points such as contours, corners, and other important features of objects, allowing robots to quickly adapt to changing conditions and diverse tasks. This is especially important in the context of Industry 5.0, where robots are expected to be not only productive, but also capable of intelligent collaboration and autonomous decision-making. In this regard, researching the possibilities of using CNNs to analyze and identify key points of objects in images is an important step towards improving the efficiency and reliability of collaborative robots in various production scenarios. Such research contributes to the development of innovative approaches to the creation of intelligent robots that meet the requirements of the new industrial era.

Related works

Robots are becoming more and more widespread nowadays. Collaborative robots are becoming especially relevant. However, their use is associated with many problems, among which we will highlight the definition of human contours and objects in the environment in general. Let's look at some recent works on this topic.

Researchers in [42] unravels the current literatures, the challenges mobile robot is being faced with.

Increasing research attention has been attracted to automatic production processes in small and medium-sized enterprises using collaborative robotic systems [43]. Authors [43] develop an object

detection solution based on deep learning on 3D point clouds for a collaborative mobile robot manipulator to automate SME production.

A robot experiment platform with stereo vision for cutting off male flower clusters of bananas is built in [44] to obtain the 3D space coordinates of the cutoff point of the rachis through visual inspection and analyze positioning errors in the depth direction.

In the research [45], performing fruit instance segmentation and the localization of picking points, a vision algorithm using RGB images was designed in a deep learning framework for a potential visual system of mango picking robots.

Scientists in [46] propose to use their Augmented Reality-based interactive robot teaching programming. This method allowed all workers even unskilled ones in robot programming, to quickly and effectively get the collision-free robot path.

The study [47] reports on a multi-robot SLAM system developed by team CoSTAR in the context of the DARPA Subterranean Challenge.

Thus, we see that the problems associated with the use of collaborative robots are extremely relevant. Further in this paper, we will consider the use of CNNs for determining key points of an object.

Mathematical Representation of the Working Principle of Convolutional Neural Networks for Analysis and Detection of Key Points in the Hand Image

The working principle of CNNs for analyzing and detecting key points in images such as hands can be described as follows. Let the input image be represented as a three-dimensional tensor X with the size $H \times W \times C$, where H is the height of the image (the number of pixels vertically); W - image width (number of pixels horizontally) and C - number of channels (for example, 3 channels for an RGB image). Then the three-dimensional tensor X can be represented as follows:

$$X = \{x_{ijk}\} \forall i \in [1, H], \forall j \in [1, W], \forall k \in [1, C] \quad (1)$$

x_{ijk} - pixel intensity value with coordinates (i, j) in channel k .

Convolution is performed using a filter (kernel) K of size $F \times F \times C$, where F is the size of the filter (usually square). The result of convolution of one filter with the input image gives a feature map Y with the size $H \times W \times 1$, which can be presented in the following form:

$$Y(i, j) = \sum_{m=1}^F \sum_{n=1}^F \sum_{c=1}^C X(i+m-1, j+n-1, c) * K(m, n, c) \quad (2)$$

$Y(i, j)$ - value on the output feature map in position (i, j) ;

X - input image or feature map from the previous layer;

i, j - coordinates on the source feature map;

m, n - indices that run through the filter sizes $F \times F$;

c - channel index (for example, for an RGB image $C = 3$);

K - is the convolution kernel applied to the input image.

F - convolution filter size (filter size), if the filter has a size 3×3 , so $F = 3$;

C - the number of channels of the input image, if it is a color image $C = 3$, if it is a black and white image $C = 1$.

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Convolution works by moving the filter K over the entire input image X and calculating the sum of the products of the pixel values under the filter and the corresponding values in the filter for each position. This process is repeated for each filter position in the input image, creating a new feature map $Y(i,j)$ that displays the result of the convolution for each position (i,j) .

At the output of the convolution, a nonlinear activation function $f()$ is applied, in the role of which the ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) function is used, which can be represented as follows:

$$\dot{Y}(i, j) = f(Y(i, j)) = \max(0, Y(i, j)) \quad (3)$$

$\dot{Y}(i, j)$ - the activated value on the output feature map in the position (i,j) , this value is the result of applying the activation function to the value $Y(i,j)$, which was obtained at the previous stage (convolution);

$f(Y(i, j))$ - the activation function applied to the value $Y(i,j)$, in this case the activation function $f()$ is ReLU. ReLU is defined as $\max(0, Y(i, j))$, which means that if $Y(i,j) > 0$, then the output value will be exactly $Y(i,j)$, otherwise, the output will be zero;

$Y(i,j)$ - output value after convolution for position (i,j) .

Formula 3 describes the activation process that adds nonlinearity to the neural network model.

After activation, pooling is performed, for example, Max Pooling, which reduces the size of the feature map. Max Pooling with window size $P \times P$ and step S is calculated as:

$$z(i, j) = \max_{m,n \in [1,P]} Y(i * S + m - 1, j * S + n - 1) \quad (4)$$

$z(i, j)$ - the value on the output feature map in the position (i,j) after the maximum summation operation;

$\max_{m,n \in [1,P]}$ - operation that finds the maximum value in a block of size $P \times P$;

$Y(i * S + m - 1, j * S + n - 1)$ - values in the input feature map \dot{Y} in position $(i * S + m - 1, j * S + n - 1)$;

S - summation step (stride), this is the number of pixels by which the summation window $P \times P$ moves when moving over the input feature map \dot{Y} .

The output maps of features after several layers of convolution and merging are transformed into a vector z , which is fed to the fully connected layer:

$$a = Wz + b \quad (5)$$

W - weight matrix;

b - displacement vector (bias);

a - output vector (logit) before activation.

For the task of detecting key points, such as the location of the joints on the hand, the fully connected layer outputs the coordinates for each key point (x_i, y_i) , and can be described as follows:

$$(x_i, y_i) = g(a_i) \quad (6)$$

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$g(\)$ - a logit-to-coordinate function, for example, through Softmax to normalize the output or through another appropriate function.

During network training, a loss function is used to compare the predicted coordinates of the key points with the actual coordinates (x_i^{true}, y_i^{true}) :

$$L = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N ((x_i - x_i^{true})^2 + (y_i - y_i^{true})^2) \quad (7)$$

N - the number of key points.

The network weights are updated using an optimization algorithm such as stochastic gradient descent (SGD) to minimize the loss function L :

$$W \leftarrow W - \eta \nabla_w L \quad (8)$$

η - learning rate;

$\nabla_w L$ - the gradient of the loss function in relation to the weights.

As can be seen, CNNs perform convolutions to extract features, apply activation functions to add nonlinearity, perform pooling to reduce feature size, use fully connected layers to predict keypoints, and optimize their weights based on a loss function to accurately detect keypoints objects such as hands in images.

Based on this, the processing of video streams and the performance of various computer vision tasks, such as the identification of hand movements based on CNNs, can be described by the following mathematical models. Let us present within the framework of these studies that the video stream is represented as a sequence of frames I_t , where t is the time index. Each frame I_t is a matrix of pixels:

$$I_t = \{I(i, j) \mid \forall i \in [1, H], j \in [1, W]\} \quad (9)$$

H and W - frame height and width, respectively.

The process of detecting a hand in a frame I_t involves the use of pre-trained neural networks. The model examines the spatial dependencies between pixels to determine the presence of a hand and find the region where it is located

$$H_{reg} = f_{dev}(I_t) \quad (10)$$

$f_{dev}(\)$ - hand detection function that outputs the bounding box coordinates $H_{reg} = [x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2]$.

Next, the process of finding key points on the hand is performed. The output function that defines the key points of the hand:

$$K_{point} = f_{K_{point}}(H_{reg}) \quad (11)$$

$f_{K_{point}}$ - function that converts a hand region into a set of keypoints $K_{point} = \{[x_i, y_i]\}$ for $i=1, 2, \dots, N$. Usually 21 key points are used for the hand, i.e. $N=21$.

The mathematical model of hand movement (M_i) can be interpreted as a sequence of changes in the coordinates of key points over time:

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$$M_i = \{[x_i(t), y_i(t)], i = 1, 2, \dots, N\} \quad (12)$$

Sequence 12 will be used for gesture identification using keypoint trajectory analysis.

A classification algorithm, for example, neural networks, is used to identify gestures. Each gesture is modeled as a certain sequence of key points:

$$G = f_g(M_i) \quad (13)$$

f_g - a classifier relating the trajectory of key points to a specific gesture.

If you look at the process of identifying hand movements based on CNNs, this process is repeated for each frame. Hand detection, key point determination and gesture classification are performed for each frame. Real-time hand motion detection is described as:

$$\{G_t\} = f_g(f_{K_{point}}(f_{dev}(I_t))) \quad (14)$$

The sequence presented in 14 allows for hand movement identification using streaming video, providing real-time recognition of hand gestures and positions.

Software implementation of Convolutional Neural Networks for analysis and detection of key points in the image of a human hand in collaborative robot working area

Python is the optimal choice for implementing a CNNs model for analyzing and detecting key points on human hand images in the workspace of a collaborative robot due to its simplicity, flexibility, and extensive set of image processing and machine learning libraries [3], [6], [8], [10], [12]. Python has a well-developed ecosystem that includes powerful libraries such as TensorFlow, Keras, and PyTorch that simplify the development and testing of neural networks. Its integration with libraries for working with images, such as OpenCV, allows efficient processing of video streams and accurate identification of objects in real time. In addition, PyCharm, as a development environment, provides an intuitive interface, convenient debugging, integration with version control, and extensive opportunities for working with large projects. PyCharm also supports various plugins and tools that make it easier to configure and manage your Python environment. Thanks to its functionality, PyCharm helps to quickly create prototypes, test hypotheses and integrate research results into software, making it an ideal choice for implementing such complex projects as CNNs for robotics in the context of Industry 5.0.

We will give an example of the implementation of some functions in the developed program for analysis and detection of key points in the image of a human hand in collaborative robot working area based on CNNs in real time.

```
hands = mp_hands.Hands(min_detection_confidence=0.7, min_tracking_confidence=0.5)
```

This piece of code creates a hand gesture recognition object, setting the minimum confidence level for hand detection and tracking. This provides more accurate gesture recognition and stable tracking of hand positions in the video stream.

```
rgb_frame = cv2.cvtColor(frame, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
results = hands.process(rgb_frame)
```

This piece of code converts the image from BGR format to RGB format, after which the hands object processes the converted image to detect hands and recognize their gestures.

```
if results.multi_hand_landmarks:
```

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```
for hand_landmarks in results.multi_hand_landmarks:  
    # Drawing points on the image  
    mp_drawing.draw_landmarks(frame, hand_landmarks,  
mp_hands.HAND_CONNECTIONS)  
  
    # Access to coordinates of key points  
    for id, landmark in enumerate(hand_landmarks.landmark):  
        h, w, c = frame.shape  
        cx, cy = int(landmark.x * w), int(landmark.y * h)  
        print(f'Landmark {id}: ({cx}, {cy})')
```

This piece of code checks to see if hands have been detected in the image, and if so, draws the key points and connections between them. It then calculates and outputs the coordinates of each key point in the image, allowing you to identify their exact positions.

The software implementation of the analysis and detection of key points in the image of a human hand in collaborative robot working area based on the CNNs in real time, through the computer vision system, is shown in Figure 1.

Based on the developed program, a number of experiments were conducted to identify key points in the image of a human hand in collaborative robot working area based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in real time. For the purity of the experiment, we note that the hardware consisted of the following elements: CPU Intel Core i7-6650U, 3.4 GHz; RAM – 16Mb; HDD - 512Gb; GPU Intel Iris Graphics 540. The obtained results are presented in Table 1, and for the convenience of visualizations for data analysis are presented in the form of graphs in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Software implementation of analysis and detection of key points in the image of a human hand in the collaborative robot working area based on CNNs in real time.

Table 1 - Results of an experiment on the detection of key points on the image of a human hand in collaborative robot working area based on a real-time CNN neural network

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Lighting conditions (lux)	FPS	Average keypoint detection accuracy (%)	Frame processing delay time (ms)	Overall tracking stability	Notes
100 lux	30	95	33	High	Bright lighting
100 lux	60	93	16	High	Bright lighting
300 lux	30	98	33	Very high	Moderate lighting
300 lux	60	96	16	Very high	Moderate lighting
500 lux	30	99	33	Excellent	Bright lighting
500 lux	60	97	16	Excellent	Bright lighting
50 lux	30	85	33	Average	Low lighting
50 lux	60	80	16	Average	Low lighting
10 lux	30	60	33	Low	Very low light
10 lux	60	50	16	Very low	Very low light

Figure 2: Comparison graph of average keypoint detection accuracy (%) and frame processing latency (ms) versus lighting conditions for two different FPS values.

Experimental results indicate a clear relationship between lighting conditions, frame rate (FPS), detection accuracy, and processing latency. As lighting conditions improve from 10 lux to 500 lux, detection accuracy increases steadily, reaching 99% at optimal lighting conditions of 500 lux at 30 FPS. This shows that a higher level of illumination significantly improves the model's ability to

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accurately identify key points on a person's hand. At 60 FPS, accuracy also improves, but shows a slight drop compared to 30 FPS, likely due to the increased processing load affecting detection quality.

Latency results show that the frame processing time decreased as the FPS increased, which is expected since the system processes fewer frames per second, but still maintains acceptable accuracy. For example, at 30 FPS the latency was 33ms in various lighting conditions, while at 60FPS it dropped to 16ms, demonstrating the advantage of high FPS in reducing processing lag.

However, under low light conditions (10 lux), the accuracy dropped significantly to 60% at 30 FPS and 50% at 60 FPS, highlighting that poor lighting seriously affects detection performance. The trade-off between detection accuracy and processing latency should be carefully controlled to optimize performance under different conditions. Overall, the results highlight the importance of proper lighting for accurate keypoint identification and indicate that balancing between FPS and lighting can improve both accuracy and real-time performance.

Conclusion

Using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to analyze and detect key points in hand images has shown significant progress in processing accuracy and speed. A mathematical representation of the working principle of CNNs showed that the model's ability to accurately identify key points increases significantly under optimal lighting conditions, reaching 99% accuracy at 500 lux and 30 FPS. At the same time, although increasing the frame rate to 60 FPS also improves accuracy, it may lead to some reduction in detection quality due to the increased processing load. Processing time experiments confirmed that high FPS reduces processing latency to 16ms, which is an advantage for real-time. However, in low light, the detection accuracy is significantly reduced, which emphasizes the importance of proper lighting to achieve high performance. The results suggest the need to balance accuracy, frame rate, and lighting conditions to optimize performance in real-time systems.

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